

Algorithm for Generating Synthetic Datasets of Lightning Flashovers on Distribution Lines

Petar Sarajcev

Department of Electrical Power Engineering

University of Split, FESB

R. Boskovicica 32, HR-21000 Split, Croatia.

petar.sarajcev@fesb.hr

Abstract—This paper describes an algorithm for generating synthetic datasets of lightning flashovers on medium voltage overhead distribution lines (OHL). Datasets are heterogeneous, hierarchical and class-imbalanced. They are designed specifically for training machine learning (ML) models (i.e. binary classifiers) for predicting lightning flashovers on OHLs, and they are built from both direct and indirect lightning strikes. Algorithm for creating datasets employs the Monte Carlo method and makes use of the several underlying mathematical models of lightning interaction with the OHL, which introduce “noise” and make training of the ML models more challenging. Algorithm is versatile enough to account for the different statistical properties of lightning interactions with distribution lines, starting from the bivariate probability distribution of lightning-current parameters. Example of the synthetic dataset will be presented, using a typical medium voltage OHL geometry with a horizontal conductors arrangement.

Index Terms—dataset, distribution line, flashover, lightning, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning has a very prominent influence on the performance and operation of medium voltage (MV) distribution overhead lines (OHLs). Lightning flashovers on the OHL insulation serve as a major source of disturbance, which is associated with outages and equipment damages. Hence, a safe and reliable OHL operation depends, to a large extent, on the lightning threats that emanate from the environment, defined by the local climate and exacerbated by the terrain and other influential features. Lightning interaction with the OHL comes in two distinct forms: (a) direct strikes and (b) indirect nearby strikes, both of which are further influenced by the presence or absence of the shield wire(s). If the shield wire is present on the line, direct strikes have two different modes by which they can provoke a flashover event: (a1) shielding failure and (a2) backflashover. The latter event can be evoked by the lightning strike to the tower top or to the shield wire along the mid-span. The shield wire is affording protection to the phase conductors by limiting the amplitudes of the prospective lightning currents that can strike them, in accordance with the electrogeometric (EGM) theory [1]. Indirect nearby strikes can trigger a flashover of the OHL insulation by the coupling of electromagnetic (EM) fields radiated from the lightning-current channel [2]. The shield wire provides screening effect to the phase conductors (from the radiated EM fields) and thus protects the OHL from indirect strikes.

Analysis of lightning flashovers on OHLs, from the direct strikes, is a straightforward matter of applying the EGM theory to the line geometry, details of which can be found in [1]. Backflashover (BFR) study, as part of the direct strike analysis, is complicated by several influential factors, such as [1, Ch.10]: frequency-dependent line parameters, corona effect, tower surge impedance, power-frequency voltage, soil ionization, etc. At the same time, analysis of lightning flashovers emanating from indirect nearby lightning strikes is far more complicated and involves very complex EM models; see, e.g., [3]–[7] for additional information. A survey of different models, with the emphasis on the validity of various approximations introduced in the overvoltage computations, is provided in [8]. A survey of the CIGRE and IEEE recommended procedures for the estimation of lightning performance of overhead transmission and distribution lines is provided in [9].

Anderson and Short in [10] presented an algorithm for computing lightning-induced voltages on distribution lines. Martinez and Gonzalez-Molina in [11] provided a statistical evaluation of lightning overvoltages on overhead distribution lines using artificial neural networks. Their approach rested on a synthetically generated dataset of lightning flashovers. Sarajcev in [12] presented a bagging ensemble machine learning (ML) model for predicting lightning flashover on distribution lines, which also rested on a synthetic dataset. Both, actual recorded lightning data [13] and artificially generated (synthetic) lightning data have their place in the data-oriented analysis of lightning flashover on OHLs [11]. In a similar vein, Machlev, et al. in [14] presented synthetic dataset generator for the analysis of power quality disturbances. It is precisely the synthetic data that is more affordable, flexible and easier to acquire in large quantities. Moreover, the level and type of noise in the synthetic dataset, along with certain other statistical properties, can be accurately controlled.

This paper presents an algorithm for generating arbitrary synthetic datasets of lightning flashovers on MV distribution lines. The proposed algorithm is based on the Monte Carlo simulation and accounts for both statistical and electromagnetic properties of the lightning interaction with OHLs. It introduces several levels of “noise” into the dataset, thereby increasing the learning challenge for the ML models. Dataset consists of different features, each with its own statistical probability distribution. It is hierarchical and class-imbalanced,

and exhibits all the main characteristics that emanate from the underlying physics of the lightning interaction with OHLs.

II. SYNTHETIC DATASETS OF LIGHTNING FLASHOVERS

Synthetic dataset of lightning flashovers, which can be employed for training different machine learning models, is generated by means of the Monte Carlo simulation. Many aspects of the dataset can be controlled by the proposed approach, from the statistical properties of different features to the type and level of noise that is intentionally injected into the dataset. The main outline of the proposed dataset construction process is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Monte Carlo method of lightning data generating process.

It can be seen that the resulting statistical probability of lightning flashovers on distribution lines, considering different modes of lightning interaction (both direct and indirect), is dependent on several statistical variables. Each of these variables, which will become features of the dataset, comes from a particular statistical probability distribution. A following comprehensive set of features has been considered (Fig. 1):

- lightning current amplitudes (I) and wavefront times (f_t), which are drawn from the appropriate bivariate *Log-Normal* distribution (with a statistical correlation between them accounted for);
- lightning return-stroke velocities (v) and lightning strike distances (d), which are independently drawn from the individual *Uniform* distributions;
- OHL tower's grounding surge impedance (R), which come from the *Normal* distribution (bounded on the left-hand side above zero);
- shield wire's presence or absence on the tower (s), which is modeled as the *Bernoulli* distribution;
- EGM model types (e), which are modeled by the *Categorical* distribution;
- induced voltage model types (c), which are depicted by a different *Categorical* distribution.

A. Statistical properties

A brief description of each feature is provided hereafter. Firstly, the bivariate *Log-Normal* distribution of the lightning-

current parameters can be elegantly generated by means of the Gaussian copula, which can be described as follows [15]:

$$c(u, v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \rho^2}} \exp\left(\frac{2\rho\xi(u, v) - \rho^2\zeta(u, v)}{2(1 - \rho^2)}\right) \quad (1)$$

with:

$$\xi(u, v) = \Phi^{-1}(u)\Phi^{-1}(v) \quad (2a)$$

$$\zeta(u, v) = \Phi^{-1}(u)^2 + \Phi^{-1}(v)^2 \quad (2b)$$

where ρ is the (linear) correlation coefficient between the variates, while Φ^{-1} is the inverse cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the univariate standard normal distribution. Next, in accordance with the well-known Sklar's theorem, an arbitrary bivariate probability density function (PDF), $f(x, y)$, can be described, in terms of the Copula approach, by the following expression [15]:

$$f(x, y) = c(F_1(x), F_2(y)) f_1(x) f_2(y) \quad (3)$$

where F_1 and F_2 represent independent (marginal) CDFs, while f_1 and f_2 denote respective marginal PDFs.

The Copula approach enables easy and fast generation of correlated random variates from the arbitrary bivariate distributions with differing and unrelated marginals [15]. First, a pseudo-random sample (u, v) is generated from the Gaussian copula, which holds a desirable correlation structure. Next, using the inverse CDFs of the independent marginal distributions, a random sample from the appropriate bivariate probability distribution is obtained as follows:

$$(x, y) = (F_1^{-1}(u), F_2^{-1}(v)) \quad (4)$$

where F_1^{-1} and F_2^{-1} are inverse CDFs of the (univariate) marginal distributions (i.e. lightning-current amplitudes and wavefront times). In this way, marginal distributions are kept independent and separated from the correlation structure of the final bivariate probability distribution, but the correlation between them will be preserved nonetheless. In case of lightning current amplitudes and wavefront times considered here, their marginal distributions are both *Log-Normal* with following parameters [16]:

$$I \sim \text{Log-N}(31.1, 0.48) \text{ kA} \quad (5a)$$

$$f_t \sim \text{Log-N}(2.83, 0.55) \mu\text{s} \quad (5b)$$

while the statistical correlation between these random variables equals 0.47. The Copula approach is just one of the ways in which random sample from the bivariate *Log-Normal* distribution can be drawn [17]. It is computationally efficient and, unlike other approaches, it can be easily extended to arbitrary multivariate cases.

Furthermore, in accordance with the above stated facts, additional statistical variables for the Monte Carlo simulation are generated as follows (Fig. 1):

$$d \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 500) \text{ m} \quad (6)$$

$$R \sim \text{Normal}(50, 12.5) \Omega, R > 0 \quad (7)$$

$$s \sim \text{Bernoulli}(0.5) \quad (8)$$

Since grounding (impulse) impedance of the tower cannot possess a negative value (it is strictly positive real number), associated *Normal* distribution is further bounded on the left-hand side above zero. Also, it is assumed that shield wire(s) are installed in only 50 % of cases, which is modeled by the *Bernoulli* distribution with the probability of 0.5. This fosters data diversity and injects “noise” into the dataset, which can be directly controlled.

Lightning return-stroke velocity can be defined by the following relationship [11]:

$$v = \frac{c}{\sqrt{1 + w/I}} \quad (9)$$

where: c is the speed of light in free space (300 m/μs), I is the lightning-current amplitude and w is a random variable:

$$w \sim \text{Uniform}(50, 500). \quad (10)$$

The EGM model can be randomly chosen from among the six different types, in accordance with a *Categorical* distribution:

$$e \sim f(x|\mathbf{p}_e) = \prod_{n=1}^6 p_n^{x_n}, \quad (11)$$

each with its own probability p_n , $n = 1, \dots, 6$, where $\sum p_n = 1$. Following EGM variants have been employed [1]: Wagner, Young, Armstrong & Whitehead, Brown & Whitehead, Love, and Anderson, with respective probabilities $p_n = [0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2]$. Using slightly different EGM variants introduces another type of “noise” into this synthetic dataset, which may compensate for some of the inherent limitations of these deterministic models of lightning interactions with overhead power lines. It also increases data diversity and, at the same time, increases a challenge for the machine learning models to learn from the data. This type of noise can also be directly controlled by the selection of EGMs and their probability p_n .

Finally, the induced voltage model type can be chosen from among the three different implementations: (a) Rusck’s model [11], (b) Chowdhuri–Gross’ model [18], and (c) Liew–Mar’s model [19], with different probability levels, as follows:

$$c \sim f(x|\mathbf{p}_c) = \prod_{i=1}^3 p_i^{x_i}, \quad (12)$$

each with its own probability p_i , $i = 1, \dots, 3$, where again $\sum p = 1$. Following probabilities are employed: $p_i = [0.4, 0.3, 0.3]$ for the three above-mentioned models, respectively. Using different induced voltage model types introduces yet additional important level of “noise” into the dataset, which further raises the level of difficulty for the model training. Namely, models (b) and (c) make use of the lightning current wavefront time when computing the induced overvoltage on the line, while model (a) does not. This can have important

repercussions on the resulting lightning flashovers probability distributions. This further level of noise is also under a direct control of the user. In case of models (b) and (c), induced overvoltage (i.e. absolute value of the first peak value of the time-domain signal) at the position on the line which is exactly perpendicular to the lightning strike location is considered when analyzing flashover events from indirect strikes.

Rusck’s model of the induced voltage calculation is the simplest from all three above-mentioned models and can be described by the following relationship [11]:

$$V_i = \frac{30I \cdot y}{x_0} \left(1 + \frac{v}{c\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{1 - 0.5 \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

where: I is the lightning current amplitude, y is the conductor height above the ground, x_0 is a perpendicular distance from the stoke point to the line, c is the velocity of light in free space (i.e. 300 m/μs), and v is the lightning return stroke velocity. It can be seen that the wavefront time of the lightning current (f_t) is absent from this relation. On the other hand, both Chowdhuri–Gross [18] and Liew–Mar [19] models are more complicated and account for the wavefront time, although they assume a linearly rising front. Interested reader is at this point advised to consult [2] for more information on these different models and their variants.

Furthermore, if the shield wire is present on the distribution line it will provide a screening effect and will reduce the overvoltage amplitude from (13) by a certain fraction, as follows:

$$V = \xi \cdot V_i, \quad (14)$$

with a factor ξ that can be computed from [11]:

$$\xi = 1 - \frac{h}{y} \cdot \frac{Z_{swc}}{Z_{sw} + 2R}, \quad (15)$$

where Z_{sw} and Z_{swc} is the wave impedance of the shield wire and its mirror image, respectively, while R is the shield wire’s grounding impedance.

B. Algorithm description

Monte Carlo simulation starts by generating a large number (e.g. $N = 10000$) samples from each of the statistical distributions. Next, it engages a lightning flashover analysis which considers a mode of lightning interaction with the distribution line (direct or indirect). Interaction mode depends on the EGM type and distance of the strike from the line. Comprehensive mathematical details of the lightning flashover analysis can be found in, e.g., [1], [2] and will not be presented here due to the space concerns. A basic outline of the computational procedure is depicted by the Algorithm 1. It is implemented in the Python programming language and the source code is available on GitHub [20].

It can be seen from the algorithm’s overall layout that, for each lightning strike, it consists of several steps. Firstly, it distinguishes if the line has shield wire(s) or not. Next, the EGM model is used to establish the striking distance and the

Algorithm 1 Lightning flashover analysis on OHLs.

```
input OHL geometry (height,  $s_g, \dots$ ).  
 $I, f, v, d, R, s, e, c \leftarrow$  Generate statistical distributions.  
flashovers  $\leftarrow$  empty(list)  
for  $x_0$  in  $d$  do  
   $r_g, r_c = EGM(I, e)$   
  if  $s = \text{True}$  then  $\triangleright$  shield wire is present  
    Compute from EGM:  $D_g(r_g, r_c)$  &  $D_c(r_g, r_c)$ .  
    if  $x_0 \leq s_g/2 + D_g$  then  
      if  $\text{bfr} = 1$  then  
         $V \leftarrow$  Compute BFR from IEEE method.  
      else if  $\text{bfr} = 2$  then  
         $V \leftarrow$  Compute BFR from CIGRE method.  
    else if  $s_g/2 + D_g < x_0 \leq s_g/2 + D_g + D_c$  then  
       $V \leftarrow$  Compute shielding failure.  
    else if  $x_0 > s_g/2 + D_g + D_c$  then  $\triangleright$  indirect strike  
      if  $c = 1$  then  
         $V_i \leftarrow$  Compute from Rusck's model.  
      else if  $c = 2$  then  
         $V_i \leftarrow$  Compute from Chowdhuri–Gross.  
      else if  $c = 3$  then  
         $V_i \leftarrow$  Compute from Liew–Mar's model.  
       $V \leftarrow k_c \cdot V_i$   $\triangleright$  screening factor  
    else  $\triangleright$  shield wire is absent  
      Compute from EGM:  $D_c(r_g, r_c)$ .  
      if  $x_0 \leq s_g/2 + D_c$  then  
         $V \leftarrow$  Compute direct strike.  
      else if  $x_0 > s_g/2 + D_c$  then  $\triangleright$  indirect strike  
        if  $c = 1$  then  
           $V \leftarrow$  Compute from Rusck's model.  
        else if  $c = 2$  then  
           $V \leftarrow$  Compute from Chowdhuri–Gross.  
        else if  $c = 3$  then  
           $V \leftarrow$  Compute from Liew–Mar's model.  
      if  $V \geq k \cdot \text{CFO}$  then  $\triangleright$  correction factor  
        flash = True  
      else  
        flash = False  
      flashovers.append(flash)  
return flashovers
```

maximum shielding current (in case of shield wires) that are then used to determine the point of lightning strike, which can be direct or indirect. A direct strike can further provoke a shielding failure or a backflashover (BFR) event. In case of the BFR, two different methods of analyzing the subsequent overvoltage are provided, the so-called IEEE and the CIGRE methods (chosen randomly by the parameter “bfr” with a 50% probability), [9]; see [1, Ch.10] for more information regarding the backflashover analysis. In case of the indirect nearby strikes, as has already been discussed, three different methods are used for analyzing the subsequent overvoltage. Finally, the overvoltage value is compared to the corrected critical flashover voltage (CFO) of the line for the onset of

the flashover event. In other words, each resulting overvoltage that exceeds the (corrected) CFO value of the line accounts for a flashover incident (event).

The resulting probability distribution of OHL flashovers can be approximated with a *Bernoulli* distribution. There is a class imbalance in the data set, due to the fact that flashover is, after all, a low probability event. This imbalance will pose a challenge to the training of ML models. There is also an inherent hierarchy in the data set, which emanates from the stochastic treatment of shield wires’ presence or absence on the line. This could be profitably exploited by the hierarchical Bayesian models. Furthermore, different types and levels of noise that were introduced to the data set can be controlled, which is important aspect of this synthetic dataset. An example of the dataset is deposited on Zenodo and is freely available under the CC BY 4.0 license [21].

III. DISTRIBUTION LINE EXAMPLE

Dataset generating process is demonstrated using a typical distribution line, on a flat terrain, with a horizontal arrangement of conductors; see [11] for more information. Height of the phase conductors is 15 m. Line has double shield wires (when installed), with a separation distance of $s_g = 3$ m and positioned 1.5 m above the phase conductors. Diameter of the phase conductor is 10 mm. Diameter of the shield wire is 5 mm. The CFO of the line insulation equals 160 kV. The coordinate system is centered on the line itself. Only downward (negative) lightning strikes are considered, without the possibility of side strikes.

Table I presents frequency distributions for the generated example data set of lightning flashovers on the considered MV overhead line. It can be seen that the class imbalance is present in the data, as expected.

TABLE I
FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF LIGHTNING FLASHOVERS ON OHL.

Events	Frequency	Relative frequency
Flashovers	1408	14.08 %
Non-flashovers	8592	85.92 %
Total:	10,000	100 %

Furthermore, Fig. 2 presents a generated example of a synthetic dataset, depicted in terms of the lightning-current amplitudes and strike distances (which are seen as two very important features). It can be seen that the Fig. 2, in addition to the scatter plot, includes marginal (statistical probability) distributions of lightning-current amplitudes and strike distances (both for the flashover and non-flashover events). Red dots in the scatter plot represent flashover events, while blue dots represent lightning strike events that did not provoke a flashover of the line insulation. Furthermore, black circle around the dots (i.e. marker edge) is used for indicating whether the overhead line had or hadn't been shielded by the shield wires for the considered lightning flash event. At the same time, Fig. 3 presents the same data (using the same markers and colors), but now as a scatter plot in the

Fig. 2. Synthetic dataset of lightning flashovers on MV overhead line, presented in terms of lightning amplitudes and strike distances.

Fig. 3. A 3D view of the select features from the synthetic dataset.

3D space, by adding a third influential feature from the dataset, which is the lightning-current wavefront times. Finally, Fig. 4 supplements the presentation by viewing these same parameters, but from the perspective of their influence on the flashover probability. Lightning strike events for which the shield wires were present on the line are here depicted with orange dots, while those without the shield wires are indicated with the blue dots.

Fig. 4. Flashover probability from the select features of the synthetic dataset.

Figs. 2, 3 and 4, when cumulatively analyzed, provide a wealth of information regarding the flashover events on overhead MV distribution lines. For example, it can be clearly seen that the direct lightning strikes practically always result with a flashover event. Furthermore, indirect nearby lightning strikes that are very close to the line can provoke flashovers even with small amplitudes. However, as the distance of the strike location is moved away from the line, the current amplitude needed for a flashover generally increases. This phenomenon, which is well-known, can also be clearly visible from the Fig. 3, where, in addition, the influence of lightning-current wavefront times can be brought into bearing on the subject. Namely, the lightning current associated with a short duration of the wavefront time (i.e. with a large steepness of the front) will induce a higher overvoltage from the indirect strike than the same current amplitude associated with a lower steepness. This means that a lightning strike with a very short wavefront time can provoke a flashover even when associated with low current amplitudes (or from a larger distance from the line). Both these aspects can be distinguished from the 3D scatter plot (see Fig. 3). Furthermore, the screening effect of the shield wires, in relation to the indirect strikes, can be recognized by the careful analysis of the edged markers' distribution on the scatter plots (both in 2D and 3D space); this effect is discernible from the Fig. 4 as well. Finally, regarding the marginal distributions of flashovers (red shaded density plots from the Fig. 2), it can be seen that the distribution of

strike locations is pushed to the left, while the distribution of amplitudes is stretched to the right (i.e. it exhibits a fat tail that the original Log–Normal distribution did not possess).

It may be interesting to analyze a particular strike event (an outlier) that provoked a flashover of the line insulation, which is represented as a red dot indicated with a magnifying glass icon on Figs. 2 and 3. It can be seen that the strike location for this event was far from the line (close to 500 m) and that the associated lightning-current amplitude was above 100 kA. Furthermore, the line didn't have shield wires installed, which eliminated the screening effect. Finally, it can be seen from the Fig. 3 that this particular strike was associated with a very short duration of the lightning-current wavefront (i.e. high steepness). It could be argued that this fact was probably the most important aspect (along with the absence of shield wires) that contributed to this particular flashover incident.

Many of the above-described features are known to be fundamental aspects of the lightning interaction with the MV overhead distribution lines, and it is comforting to see them revealed in this synthetic data set; e.g. see [1], [2] for more information on the underlying physics. For example, it is quite clear that, on the basis of Fig. 2 alone, one could determine (even by just looking at the distribution of blue and red dots) the “critical flashover curve” of the line that Anderson and Short provided in [10]; see also [12] for additional information. Many of these aspects, at the same time, corroborate that the procedure of generating this artificial data has been able to capture all the main characteristics of the physical processes of lightning interactions with the OHLs. The reason behind that lies in the fact that the data-generating process itself rests on the solid fundamentals of the EGM theory and three well-known models of indirect lightning interaction with the overhead lines.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an algorithm for generating synthetic datasets of lightning flashovers on distribution lines. These artificially created data sets could be employed for training machine learning models (i.e. binary classifiers) for predicting outages of MV overhead lines due to lightning. It ought to be mentioned that this kind of real-world data is very hard to come by, and can be expensive to acquire when available. On the other hand, the proposed algorithm can produce versatile datasets of different lengths, for different line geometries and voltage levels. Datasets can further have hierarchical structure and feature different levels of class imbalance. Furthermore, different types and levels of “noise” that are introduced to the dataset can be directly controlled by the user. The proposed approach employs the EGM theory, two different methods of backflashover analysis, and three different models of indirect lightning interaction with the OHLs. This makes it well aligned with the relevant CIGRE and IEEE recommendations. Finally, the presented dataset example exhibits many of the features commonly associated with actual lightning flashovers on OHLs.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. R. Hileman, *Insulation Coordination for Power Systems*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 1999.
- [2] P. Chowdhuri, *Electromagnetic Transients in Power Systems*. Taunton, England: Research Studies Press Ltd, 1996.
- [3] A. K. Agrawal, H. J. Price, and S. H. Gurbaxani, “Transient response of multiconductor transmission lines excited by a nonuniform electromagnetic field,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. EMC-22, no. 2, pp. 119–129, 1980.
- [4] G. Diendorfer, “Induced voltage on an overhead line due to nearby lightning,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 292–299, 1990.
- [5] R. Pokharel, M. Ishii, and Y. Baba, “Numerical electromagnetic analysis of lightning-induced voltage over ground of finite conductivity,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 651–656, 2003.
- [6] H. Hoidalen, “Analytical formulation of lightning-induced voltages on multiconductor overhead lines above lossy ground,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 92–100, 2003.
- [7] H.-M. Ren, B.-H. Zhou, V. A. Rakov, L.-H. Shi, C. Gao, and J.-H. Yang, “Analysis of lightning-induced voltages on overhead lines using a 2-D FDTD method and Agrawal coupling model,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 651–659, 2008.
- [8] V. Cooray and V. Scuka, “Lightning-induced overvoltages in power lines: Validity of various approximations made in overvoltage calculations,” *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 355–363, 1998.
- [9] C. Nucci, “A survey on CIGRE and IEEE procedures for the estimation of the lightning performance of overhead transmission and distribution lines,” in *2010 Asia-Pacific International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 2010, pp. 1124–1133.
- [10] J. Anderson and T. Short, “Algorithms for calculation of lightning induced voltages on distribution lines,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1217–1225, 1993.
- [11] J. Martinez and F. Gonzalez-Molina, “Statistical evaluation of lightning overvoltages on overhead distribution lines using neural networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 2219–2226, 2005.
- [12] P. Sarajcev, “Bagging ensemble classifier for predicting lightning flashovers on distribution lines,” in *Proceedings of 7th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies*, 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [13] H. D. Betz, K. Schmidt, P. Laroche, P. Blanchet, W. P. Oettinger, E. Defer, Z. Dziewit, and J. Konarski, “LINET—An international lightning detection network in Europe,” *Atmospheric Research*, vol. 91, no. 2–4, pp. 564–573, 2009.
- [14] R. Machlev, A. Chachkes, J. Belikov, Y. Beck, and Y. Levron, “Open source dataset quality disturbances with deep-learning reference classifiers,” in *International Conference on Power Systems Transients (IPST2021)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [15] X. Hu, J. He, and H. Ly, “Generating multivariate nonnormal distribution random numbers based on copula function,” *Journal of Information and Computing Science*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 191–196, 2007.
- [16] CIGRE WG, “Lightning parameters for engineering applications,” CIGRÉ, Paris, Brochure 549, 2013, Working Group C4.407.
- [17] A. Borghetti, C. Nucci, and M. Paolone, “An improved procedure for the assessment of overhead line indirect lightning performance and its comparison with the IEEE Std. 1410 method,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 684–692, 2007.
- [18] P. Chowdhuri, “Analysis of lightning induced voltages on overhead lines,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 479–492, 1989.
- [19] A. Liew and S. Mar, “Extension of the Chowdhuri-Gross model for lightning induced voltage on overhead lines,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. PWRD-1, no. 2, pp. 240–247, 1986.
- [20] P. Sarajcev, “distlines,” <https://github.com/sarajcev/distlines>, 2022, GitHub.
- [21] —, “Dataset of lightning flashovers on medium voltage distribution lines (ver. 1.0),” <https://zenodo.org/record/7382548>, 2022, Zenodo.